

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF THE QUALITY OF DRINKS BASED ON RECONSTITUTED JUICES FROM FREEZE-DRIED PLANT MATERIALS

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Abstract

This work has never been done before. This was done in shorthand 5 samples from 120 samples (powder, puree, extract) the development of a non-alcoholic drink based on freeze-dried natural fruit and berry powders. The analysis of reconstituted juices and non-alcoholic products of a domestic manufacturer based on vegetable raw materials was carried out. The quality indicators of non-alcoholic beverages were studied in accordance with the requirements of regulatory documentation. The pH, density and viscosity of the developed samples were analyzed, the mass fraction of dry substances was determined by the refractometric method, as well as the acidity by the potentiometric titration method. The organoleptic evaluation of soft drinks was carried out by the descriptor-profile method with the construction of profilograms. As a result of the analysis of identification indicators, it was found that the studied samples of drinks have high organoleptic characteristics. The duration of storage for 30 days at 6-8 °C had no effect on pH, viscosity and sensory parameters. Precipitate in the prepared drinks after storage in refrigerated conditions within a month was not formed.

Keywords: natural fruit powder, puree, extract, quality indicators, soft drink, regulatory documentation, tasting

Introduction.

There is a strong demand for soft drinks around the world. In most countries, drinks are prepared using flavors, colors, sweeteners and the addition of CO₂. But in general, the soft drink industry is developing very dynamically, the range is constantly expanding due to drinks made from concentrates, infusions of aromatic raw materials, which not only have pleasant taste properties, but also have a positive effect on the organs and systems of the body when included in the diet [1].

With a general reduction in demand for traditional soft drinks, there is simultaneously a growing demand for drinks with health claims. The nutritional value of fruits and vegetables, in addition to containing a significant amount of sugars, starch, as well as nitrogenous substances, which are nutrients, increases the vital activity of the body, improves digestion and the absorption of proteins and fats. Most juices and drinks have a significant sugar content in their composition, so there is a prospect of creating drinks based on vegetable and fruit powders without added sugar [2].

In ancient Russian sources, cucumber pickle, sauerkraut juice, fruit drinks, kvass, lingonberry water and other berry waters, simple and spiced honeys are called native Russian drinks. Of the ancient Russian drinks, such as hot sbiten, kvass, voditsa or vodichkek, only kvass has survived today. Vodichki have been the most popular drinks in Russia for centuries [3].

The range of non-alcoholic products, both on the world market and in Russia, is expanding, mainly due to the use of new, non-traditional types of raw materials, as well as various food additives that improve their

organoleptic and physicochemical properties, but are not always associated with benefits for consumer health [1].

Formulation of the problem.

The range of soft drinks is replenished with more and more new products every year. Not all of them are made from natural raw materials. Manufacturers often mislead consumers by using chemical additives without indicating this on the packaging. But to satisfy the human body in the vitamin-mineral complex, it is advisable to solve it through soft drinks, in which these nutrients are in a liquid state, in combination with glucose, which allows the metabolism to enter the blood as quickly as possible. Therefore, it is relevant to develop soft drinks based on natural fruit and berry powders obtained by freeze-drying. The purpose of the scientific research was to develop a soft drink Through three stages (Powder - Extract - puree) based on natural fruit powders and study quality indicators. To achieve this goal, the following tasks had to be solved:

- Select the most promising herbal supplements from the available range of herbal powders, the most popular among the population;
- Select a range of quality and safety indicators for soft drinks;
- Check the compliance of the samples under study with the requirements of the Technical Regulations regarding the production process and nutritional value of food products;
- Examine samples of soft drinks according to organoleptic and physicochemical indicators;

- Establish the compliance of the studied samples of soft drinks with organoleptic and physico-chemical indicators with the requirements of the legislation of the Russian Federation.

Literature review.

Fruits and berries have a high content of vitamins and minerals. Juices, nectars, and soft drinks made from them are healthy and are constantly in demand among consumers. But these are seasonal raw materials and it is not always possible to prepare a large amount of raw materials for future use, prepare a large amount of juices at the same time, or preserve grown fruits and berries, especially wild ones, until the next harvest. An alternative to this process is low-temperature technology for processing these raw materials. The most promising method is freeze drying of fruits and berries. This is achieved by removing moisture from raw materials with a residual amount of up to 5% [4]. This product can be stored in vacuum packaging for up to three years at a temperature of 20 °C and a humidity of 65-70% [5]. At the same time, their biologically active composition does not change. The resulting berry powder can serve as the basis for preparing non-alcoholic vitamin drinks. In order to increase the nutritional and biological value, various blends of powders can be prepared, which increases the possibility of obtaining a pronounced pleasant or exotic perception, manifested in a special way of color.

Russian drinks are known from literary sources: lingonberry, red currant, cranberry water and other drinks made from berry juices (cranberries, cloudberries, raspberries, wild strawberries, red and black currants, gooseberries, blackberries, blueberries). Searches for the most nutritionally and microbiologically attractive raw materials B.M. Zhirov, S.Yu. Makarov, S.S. Makarov and O.P. Presnyakova [3] made a trial recipe for water based on lingonberries and cranberries. These berries were chosen because they contain natural preservatives: benzoic and chlorogenic acids, which should increase the stability of the drink during storage.

In the task of obtaining new technologies and recipes I.V. Ivanova, D.A. Kozodaeva, M.V. Konovalov and A.Yu. Grigorieva [2] included the development of the nutrient balance of powdered vegetable or fruit mixtures for the preparation of soft drinks. This was achieved by comparing the beneficial qualities of fruit and vegetable powders, which serve as an alternative to canned juices. Juices consisting of two or more components are more nutritious, therefore, in order to enrich the mixture, tomato and pumpkin powders had to be enriched with the inclusion of additional powders that differ in nutrient composition and improve the organoleptic properties of the finished product. These are a mixture of pumpkin and apple, as well as tomatoes, green onions and dill in given proportions [2].

Similar drinks were prepared by Moiseeva M.V. [6]. The drinks are developed on the basis of pumpkin puree with the addition of medicinal plant extracts and are intended to replenish the lack of energy and regulatory food substances in the body.

Comparing apple monojuice and a drink prepared on the basis of pumpkin and apple powder I.V. Ivanova and co-authors claim that this soft drink becomes richer

in B vitamins, vitamin A, β -carotene and dietary fiber [2].

When comparing drinks based on a tomato-onion-dill mixture and regular store-bought tomato juice, the prepared non-alcoholic drink with a developed powder-based recipe has a clear advantage (in terms of nutritional value - in all respects, and the content of vitamin K, which affects coagulability and physiological parameters blood, is replenished by 100%) [2, 7]. Similar results were obtained by O.A. Ryazanova, O.D. Kirilicheva [7], as well as Paul Paquin [8].

Komrakova N.A. and Filonova G.L. scientifically substantiated the formation of mixtures from plant raw materials to obtain multicomponent concentrates and drinks based on them, containing a minimum sufficient mass of granulated sugar introduced from outside into their composition [9]. Based on a preliminary study of the composition and properties of plant raw materials, organically combined plant mixtures were identified for the subsequent production of concentrates, infusions, and extracts from them. This approach contributes to the formation of an individual functional orientation, taste, color range, and stable texture in a soft drink.

The technological process developed by the authors proceeds in a mild temperature regime of exposure to raw materials, which allows preserving biologically active substances in their native form. The drinks are based on the properties of nutrients, including biologically active ones, which influence the formation of the taste qualities of the soft drink. The developed drink is capable of providing not only health-improving and preventive effects, but also exhibiting original flavor tones, quenching thirst and refreshing [9].

A number of authors (Filonova G.L., Kovaleva I.L., Komrakova N.A., Shcherbakova V.V., Nikiforova E.V., Osipova V.P., Grishkovsky B.A.) [14] consider technologies, which successfully use natural flavors. Most of their main components are essential oils. It should be noted the high quality of domestic industrially produced natural flavors, for example, the flavor "Isindi" (flavor of laurel and apple), "Cherry" (flavor of cherry compote), "Berry" (flavor of ripe raspberries), "Ginger" (flavor of hot ginger), "Herbs" (thyme aroma), "Vegetable" (lightly salted cucumber), etc.

The flavor spectrum is formed by tannins and, in particular, tannin. The natural complex of nutrients from plant and fruit and berry raw materials contains tannins that have a tart, astringent taste. Condensed tannins are not esters and do not hydrolyze. These include catechins [10 - 13]. Tannins are found in large quantities in sloe, mountain ash, black currant, bird cherry, oak, quince, pine, chamomile, sage, barberry, hawthorn, motherwort, etc. [9].

Thus, at present, the most important is the development of science-based technologies for multicomponent concentrates (cryopowders) for drinks with targeted functional properties using plant raw materials, guided by the principles of food combinatorics. This will make it possible, in conditions of sports substitution, to saturate the market with good-quality food products, and, in particular, reconstituted juices and soft drinks.

Materials and research methods.

To develop soft drinks from a domestic manufacturer, samples of freeze-dried powders were selected: stage N°1 and 2 for Powders and purees (Raspberry honeysuckle, Sea buckthorn, lingonberry, Honeysuckle, blueberry, Red currant) with 45 Samples for each! total 90 samples - stage N°3 for Extracts (Thyme Extract, Valerian Extract, Propolis Extract, Raspberry Extract, Blackberry Extract) with 30 Samples; The drink's recipe included citric acid and sugar. Drinks were prepared using distilled water. The finished products were compared with the requirements of the Technical Regulations regarding food safety TR CU 021/2011 [15]. The determination of organoleptic indicators was carried out according to GOST 6687.5-86

[16], as well as GOST 28188-2014 [17], GOST R 51823 [18] and GOST R 53193 [19]. Physicochemical indicators, namely acidity according to GOST 33776-2016: Test methods for chemical products that pose a danger to the environment. Determination of pH, acidity and alkalinity [20]. Method for determining acidity GOST 6687.5-86 Products of the non-alcoholic industry [21]. Dry matter content – GOST 6687.2-90 [22].

Results and its discussion.

Table 1 – Rating assessment of sensory indicators of Powders P1 (Lingonberry + Honeysuckle) And Purees PP2 (Raspberry honeysuckle + Sea buckthorn + Lingonberry + Blueberry) And Extracts E3/E4/E5 (Propolis + Raspberry + Blackberry / Thyme + Raspberry / Valerian + Propolis + Raspberry)

№	Indicator (descriptor)	Experts (points)						Σ points	Descriptor Rank
		1	2	3	4	5	6		
1	Previous taste	9	9	10	9	8	10	55	X
2	Aftertaste	8	7	8	9	8	10	50	VIII
3	Harmony of components	8	8	9	9	9	9	52	IX
4	Textural characteristics	5	4	5	5	5	5	29	III
5	Aesthetics of the product	8	9	7	6	8	7	45	VI
6	Ergonomics	7	7	7	6	7	8	42	V
7	No foreign taste	8	7	8	7	7	9	46	VII
8	Homogeneity of structure	3	4	3	3	4	4	21	I
9	The influence of flavor on psychophysical parameters	6	5	5	5	5	5	31	IV
10	Flavor decay rate when cooled to 25 °C	4	4	4	4	4	4	24	II

Based on the results of the rating assessment drinks, it can be seen that the total score for the X descriptor is 57 points, which, in turn, is higher than the rating of the cupcake, but less than the rating of the cookies.

Based on the assessment results, a drawing was constructed according to the rank of the descriptor and the sum of its points for all developed products (Fig. 1).

Based on the results of the expert assessment, it is clear that the descriptors make it possible to give a comprehensive organoleptic characteristics of the finished products. The proposed soft drinks are similar in quality characteristics, as demonstrated by I - X descriptors. To assess the impartiality of experts, it was decided to

carry out an expert examination of key descriptors (VII – X) (Fig. 1).

Based on the results of the organoleptic evaluation of the drinks, we can conclude that all samples are of good quality. The results are shown in table. 2

Table. 2

Powder And Puree And Extract	Recipe	Viscosity	Ph after 10D Ph after 20D	Hydrometer 20C g/ml	Photomètre Optical density, nm, after 10 days	Taste/Color	Smell
Thyme extract + Raspberry extract E3	2g Powder + 2g citric acid + 100g sugar + 100 ml drinking water	09.205	2.275 2.763	1.099	0.030 514.2	5 /5	4 /5
Propolis extract + Raspberry extract + Blackberry extract E4	3g Powder + 3g citric acid + 100g sugar + 100 ml drinking water	11.375	2.634 2.628	1.087	0.030 682.1	5 /5	5 /5
Valerian extract + Propolis extract + Raspberry extract E5	3g Powder + 3g citric acid + 100g sugar + 100 ml drinking water	10.229	2.656 2.652	1.068	0.030 637.2	5 /5	5 /5
Raspberry honeysuckle + Sea buckthorn + Lingonberry + Blueberry P1	4g Powder + 4g citric acid + 100g sugar + 100 ml drinking water	11.377	2.435 2.430	1.038	0.030 710.3	5/5	4 /5
Lingonberry + Honeysuckle PP2	2g Powder + 2g citric acid + 100g sugar + 100 ml drinking water	12.412	2.435 2.421	1.044	0.030 832.1	4/5	5 /5

It was revealed that the content and safety of nutrients in products processing of berries, fruits and vegetables, such as dry powders and extracts, is not the same and depends on the production method. Study of

the vitamin composition of powders from extracts and pulp strawberries, raspberries, blackberries and blueberries show different preservation water-soluble vitamins C, PP and B1 (Table 3).

Table 3

Content of water-soluble vitamins in powders from extract and pulp of berries from the Moscow region after 30 days of storage

Name of samples	Vitamin C, 100g/ mg	Vitamin B1, 100g/ mg	Vitamin PP, 100g/ mg
Dry strawberry extract	34,14 ± 0,007	0,03 ± 0,005	0,18 ± 0,009
Dry strawberry powder	44,21 ± 0,011	-	0,07 ± 0,001
Dry raspberry extract	17,41 ± 0,010	0,027 ± 0,001	0,51 ± 0,004
Dry raspberry powder	9,29 ± 0,003	-	0,26 ± 0,003
Dry blackberry extract	16,21 ± 0,012	0,0298 ± 0,002	0,187 ± 0,001
Dry blackberry powder	3,28 ± 0,014	-	0,152 ± 0,004
Dry blueberry extract	8,76 ± 0,010	0,012 ± 0,001	0,164 ± 0,008
Dry blueberry powder	3,54 ± 0,005	-	0,359 ± 0,006

It was found that the maximum preservation of water-soluble vitamins for a month was found in extracts of berries and vegetables. Received: vitamin PP

in high concentration in sweet pepper powder; C and B1 - in dill powder. For berries, the best results were obtained from strawberry and raspberry powder.

Figure 2: Concentration of glucose in powders

The purpose of using the method (Photoelectrocolorimetric ferricyanide), see the concentration of glucose in the powders using a calibration graph

It has been established that the amount of reducing sugars in drinks increases depending on the content of organic acids in berry powders and extracts

Conclusions.

As a result of the analysis of identification indicators, it was established that the studied samples of drinks have high organoleptic indicators. Storage for 30 days at 6-8 °C had no effect on pH, viscosity and sensory characteristics. No sediment formed in the prepared drinks after storage in refrigeration for a month. Dry sea Powders P1 (Lingonberry + Honeysuckle) And Purees PP2 (Raspberry honeysuckle + Sea buckthorn + Lingonberry + Blueberry) And Extracts E3/E4/E5 (Propolis + Raspberry + Blackberry / Thyme + Raspberry / Valerian + Propolis + Raspberry) the requirements of TR CU 021/2011.

References:

- Gulevataya M. A., Usatyuk S. I. Study of quality indicators of soft drinks. //Scientific Journal "Science Rise" No. 5/2(4), 2014. – p 10-14. DOI: 10.15587/23138416.2014.31498
- Ivanova, I.V. Development of a recipe for a mixture of vegetable and fruit powders for the preparation of soft drinks /Ivanova I.V., Kozodaeva D.A., Konovalov M.V., Grigorieva A.Yu. // Technologies of the food and processing industry of the agro-industrial complex - healthy food products, No. 3, 2015. – P. 26-33.
- Zhirov, V.M. Forgotten recipes for Russian drinks / B.M. Zhirov, S.Yu. Makarov, S.S. Makarov, O.P. Presnyakova. // Beer and drinks, 2015. - No. 1. – pp. 26-29.
- Cranberry powder. http://sinref.ru/000_uchebniki/04200produkti/008_ Date of access: 02/19/2023.
- How to properly store cranberries? <http://kakhranit.ru/kak-nuzhno-pravilnoxranit-klyukvu/> Date of access: 02/19/2023.
- Moiseeva, M.V. Drinks based on vegetable raw materials [Text] / M.V. Moiseeva, M.K. Altunyan // Young scientist. - 2013. - No. 5. - P. 86-88.
- Ryazanova, O.A. The use of local plant raw materials in the production of fortified products [Text] / O.A. Ryazanova, O.D. Kirilicheva // Food industry. - 2005. - No. 6. - P. 72.
- Paquin, Paul Functional drinks and specialty drinks. [Text] / Paul Paquin. - St. Petersburg: Professional Publishing House, 2010. - 495 p.
- Komrakova, N.A. Rational level of carbohydrates added to soft drinks using components from plant raw materials / N.A. Komrakov; G.L. Filonova. // Beer and drinks, 2014. No. 5. – pp. 20-25.
- Putyrsky, I.N. Medicinal plants. Encyclopedia / I.N. Putyrsky, V.A Prokhorov. - Minsk: Book House, 2002. - pp. 27-39.
- Weixin, W. Healing powers of nature: Encyclopedia of Chinese medicine / W. Weixin. - St. Petersburg; Neva; M.: OLMA-PRESS, 2002. - pp. 290-315.
- Kretovich, V. L. Fundamentals of plant biochemistry / V. L. Kretovich. - M.: Higher School, 1971. - P. 152-153.
- Fedorova, O. V. Drinks and semi-finished products from natural raw materials / O. V. Fedorova, G. L. Filonova // Beer and drinks. - 2012. - No. 4. - P. 74-75.
- Food combinatorics in the technologies of multicomponent concentrates using plant raw materials and drinks based on them / G. L. Filonova [et al.] // Beer and drinks. - 2013. - No. 1. - P. 10.

15. Technical Regulations of the Customs Union TR CU 021/2011 On food safety (as amended as of July 14, 2021).
16. GOST 6687.5-86 Products of the non-alcoholic industry. Methods for determining organoleptic indicators and production volume. An amendment was made, published in IUS No. 7, 2007.
17. GOST 28188-2014. Non-alcoholic drinks. General technical conditions.
18. GOST R 51823 Alcohol products and raw materials for their production.
19. GOST R 53193 Alcoholic and non-alcoholic drinks.
20. GOST 33776-2016: Test methods for chemical products that pose a danger to the environment.
21. GOST 6687.5-86 Products of the non-alcoholic industry. Methods for determining acidity.
22. GOST 6687.2-90. Products of the non-alcoholic industry. Methods for determining dry substances.